

Potentials for reducing spatial inequalities in innovation: A spatial econometric perspective

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Capabilities of regions to create new knowledge are a major source of regional inequalities in innovation and, thus, economic competitiveness in the long run. Aiming to identify potentials for reducing such inequalities, we analyse the extent to which disparities in regional technological knowledge stocks can be explained by specific features of regional knowledge bases. Specifically, we shift attention to characteristics recently discussed in the context of regional innovation capabilities, among them, indicators capturing the relatedness of the technological fields a region is active in, a region's knowledge complexity, and the technological complementarity of neighbouring regions. We implement a spatial Durbin model for 430 European regions. While high technological complementarity of spatially close regions and a high relatedness of the region's technological capacities are conducive to regional innovation, knowledge complexity exhibits a negative indirect effect. In illustrative convergence scenarios, we demonstrate the potential of increasing regional relatedness and spatial complementarity values for reducing inequalities in Europe.

1. Introduction

Europe is characterized by significant socio-economic inequalities across regions. The investigation of these inequalities has a long-standing research tradition and has become a central issue of concern in the public policy debate. While the literature of the last decades has primarily analysed inequality with respect to economic indicators, focusing on drivers of regional economic growth (see, e.g., Cörvers & Mayhew, 2021; Iammarino et al., 2019; McCann, 2020), this article shifts attention to disparities in terms of place-based capabilities for generating innovations. The latter is widely considered as one of the most crucial determinants of a region's competitiveness and economic productivity in the long-term. Regional innovative capabilities are assumed to be strongly related to the underlying characteristics of a region's knowledge endowments and production capacities. Understanding how disparities in terms of knowledge production capacities as a basis for regional innovation can be reduced, is therefore essential for identifying potentials to reduce inter-regional disparities in terms of economic performance and welfare and to prevent regions from falling into a development trap (see e.g.).

The objective of this study is thus (i) to identify drivers of disparities in terms of regional knowledge creation, and (ii) to illustrate under which conditions potentials for convergence may be leveraged. While the investigation of drivers of regional knowledge production is by no means new to the literature (see, for instance Wanzenböck & Piribauer, 2018; Wanzenböck et al., 2020), this article shifts attention to the technological knowledge stock, and on the role played by the technological structure of both the region-internal and the region-external knowledge portfolio, reflected by concepts that came into debate recently, namely, technological *relatedness*, *knowledge complexity* and technological *complementarity* of external knowledge sources.

Knowledge creation is traditionally understood as a process of combining and recombining existing ideas (Weitzman, 1998). Following a well-established literature, we acknowledge that not all types of existing knowledge pieces can be recombined equally well and argue that a high cognitive proximity of technologies present in a region – here defined as average *relatedness density* of technologies a region is specialized in – facilitates the recombination of knowledge and, thus, stimulates regional innovation (see also Miguelez & Moreno, 2018; Castaldi et al., 2015). We also reflect on knowledge complexity, which indicates the ability of a region to create a diversified portfolio of knowledge, and at the same time, export rare and specialised knowledge available only in a few other places (Balland et al., 2019; Pintar & Scherngell, 2022). While complexity has been linked with higher economic growth (Pintar & Scherngell, 2022; Rigby et al., 2022), its impact on the overall knowledge output is still unknown.

The innovative activity of a region is not only determined by the characteristics of its local knowledge base, but also relies heavily on its access to region-external knowledge. The latter prevents the region from a lock-in situation allowing for the inflow of new knowledge domains (Bathelt et al., 2004; Boschma, 2005). Hereby, different authors have theorized that what matters is not being linked to regions per se, but rather the cognitive proximity between the external knowledge flows and the local knowledge base (Boschma & Iammarino, 2009; Miguelez & Moreno, 2018). Boschma and Iammarino (2009) find that this cognitive proximity is ideally neither too large nor too small, allowing for novel knowledge pieces, while guaranteeing that local agents have the absorptive capacity to exploit the link to the external knowledge base. Building on these insights, we want to explore how technological *complementarity* and technological *relatedness* of the knowledge bases of linked regions contribute to the local knowledge creation capacity. Unlike previous studies, which mostly captured (the relatedness of) external knowledge flows using trade data, patent collaborations or patent citations (Boschma & Iammarino, 2009; Miguelez & Moreno, 2018), we consider the *complementarity* and *relatedness* of the knowledge base of both (i) neighbouring regions and (ii) regions that are connected via research and development (R&D) networks. Thereby we acknowledge that knowledge is transmitted through relational proximity in the form of common R&D projects (Fornahl et al., 2011; Wanzenböck & Piribauer, 2018), but also in the form of geographically bounded knowledge spillovers (Fischer et al., 2009; Jaffe et al., 1993). Especially the aspect of the latter, namely the role played by spatial proximity to external knowledge bases that are complementary and related to the local knowledge base, is yet neglected in empirical research.

We employ a spatial econometric framework in form of a spatial Durbin model (SDM). Conceptually, our empirical model is inspired by the literature stream using a Knowledge Production Function (KPF) framework. We study the impact of the region internal technological structure – reflected by technological relatedness and complexity on the region’s knowledge creation activity, but also the impact of the relatedness and complementarity of spatially close regions, and regions linked via common R&D projects. The spatial econometric approach allows us to account for both spatial endogeneity of the dependent variable and to capture spatial spillover effects emanating from the explanatory variables.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: In the next section we discuss the conceptual foundations of (technological) relatedness, complementarity and knowledge complexity and their relation to knowledge creation. We then outline the operationalisation of the main variables and introduce the model and the data. In Section 3, we present the results of the SDM and provide descriptive scenarios, reflecting the untapped potential in complementarity and relatedness in lagging regions that could foster cohesion. We close with a short discussion of our results.

2. Conceptual Background

For a long time, the economic development literature has been concerned about the identification of factors driving or deterring economic convergence across regions. Authors have pointed to the persisting regional economic inequality in Europe as underpinned by the existence of several development groups of regional economies – also referred to as spatial regimes, (see Fischer & Stirböck, 2006), which differ significantly in their place-specific endowments of skill sets, human capital, connectivity, industry structure, the quality of formal and informal institutions and – in the focus of this article – their knowledge base and innovation potential (Diemer et al., 2022; Iammarino et al., 2019). Since the 2008 crisis, attention is not only paid to the economic catch-up of the lowest income regions, but also to a group of “left behind”, “development-trapped” middle-income regions, suffering from long term economic stagnation, often accompanied by social and political tensions, reflected by a rise in populist parties (Pike et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Pose, 2018). Building on a big body of literature stressing the role of innovative capacities in shaping the economic performance of a region (Maggioni et al., 2007), it has been argued that it is their inability to break into innovation-intensive industries preventing these stagnating regions from fully catching up (Diemer et al., 2022; Kharas & Kohli, 2011). Thus, understanding drivers of innovation, and therewith associated, knowledge creation activities, is not only a prerequisite for the catch-up of low-income regions, but particularly relevant for stagnating middle-income regions.

Beginning in the 1990s, the geography of innovation literature has argued that knowledge creation typically concentrate in space, resulting in big gaps across regions (Audretsch & Feldman, 1996; Feldman, 1994). This is partly explained by urbanization economies, reflecting that innovation is encouraged in dense, urban areas, as these are typically associated with a highly skilled workforce, such as a dense presence of knowledge-generating institutions that benefit from each other via localized knowledge spillovers (Frenken et al., 2007). Central to these agglomeration tendencies is the cumulative nature of innovation, referring to the traditional understanding of knowledge creation as a process of recombining previously

existing local ideas and technologies (Weitzman, 1998), or put differently, the idea that new knowledge is built upon current and existing knowledge bases (Antonelli, 2005). In the context of spatial agglomeration of knowledge, this recombinant nature of innovation implies that regions that already have a diverse knowledge base to draw from, have greater potential for future innovation, as existing ideas can more easily be recombined to new knowledge (Castaldi et al., 2015; Jacobs, 1969). In this vein, more recent contributions have pointed out that not all diversity is equally effective in promoting the creation of new knowledge (Boschma et al., 2008). Under the notion of *related variety*, different authors (see for instance Frenken et al., 2007) argue that the extent to which regions can engage in recombinant innovation, depends on whether the technological fields present in a region are related, i.e., whether the underlying knowledge domains of said technologies exhibit similarities. The underlying idea is that a high relatedness, i.e., cognitive proximity, of technologies present in a region, may facilitate the recombination of knowledge and thus stimulate the regional innovation processes (Miguelez & Moreno, 2018). Applying these findings to a region's overall knowledge creation capacity, we expect that a high degree of relatedness among technologies that a region is specialized in, acts as a driver of regional knowledge output, and therefore yields potentials for reducing disparities across regions.

We also reflect on the concept of regional knowledge complexity (Balland et al., 2019; Pintar & Scherngell, 2022) as another potential driver of regional technological knowledge creation. A region's knowledge complexity is defined by its ability to create knowledge in a diverse set of knowledge domains, but also in knowledge domains of low ubiquity, i.e., technologies that are not produced by many other regions. Complex knowledge is generally associated with a high degree of tacitness, a decreased accessibility for others and thus increased spatial stickiness and is seen as a major source of competitive advantage for regions (Balland & Rigby, 2017). It has been associated with higher economic growth rates (Pintar & Scherngell, 2022) such as a higher level of GDP per capita (Pinheiro et al., 2022), which makes knowledge complexity an interesting aspect to be studied in the context of regional inequality. Its relation to the overall knowledge stock is yet unclear. Given that complexity is a relative, rather than an absolute measure, it may be argued that it does not affect the volume, but just the specificity of knowledge production.

It is well accepted that knowledge production is not only determined by region-internal capacities and local interactions but is also heavily dependent on external knowledge flows. These avoid that regions get locked-in in existing activities and are thus crucial for a region's innovative activity (Bathelt et al., 2004; Boschma & Lambooy, 1999; Crespo et al., 2014). There are different understandings of how exactly external-knowledge diffusion occurs. While some scholars have stressed the importance of long-distance ties for knowledge transmission, arguing that knowledge is increasingly spread and created in non-spatially bounded, formal research and development (R&D) networks, i.e., via collaborations across knowledge-intensive organizations (Crescenzi et al., 2020; Thomas Scherngell, 2013; Wanzenböck & Piribauer, 2018), others point to the existence of spatial knowledge spillovers across spatially close agents, arguing that the spread of knowledge is underlying a strong geographical bias (Fischer et al., 2009, Jaffe et al., 1993). While the central role of knowledge spillovers via formal R&D collaborations and between neighbouring regions is well documented, the literature has long

been silent on whether the technological structure of the external knowledge base determines how much a region can benefit from these external links in terms of knowledge creation. Only Boschma and Iammarino (2009) – explaining growth in Italian regions, Tavassoli and Carbonara (2014) for Swedish innovation and, more recently, Miguelez and Moreno (2018) for innovation in European regions and Wang et al. (2023) for Chinese cities, have demonstrated, that regional innovative activity is encouraged by external knowledge flows that are similar (Miguelez & Moreno, 2018) or related, but not identical, to the local knowledge base (Boschma & Iammarino, 2009; Wang et al., 2023). In a similar vein, Balland and Boschma (2021) recently, introduced the concept of *complementarity* to the technological diversification literature, showing that being connected to regions that hold *complementary* capacities for a certain technology, i.e., capabilities in technologies which are related to this technology and not present in the own portfolio yet, increases the regions probability to develop a new technological specialization in said technology. Based on previous findings of the literature, suggesting that regions benefit from external knowledge that (i) can be absorbed by the local actors, while (ii) also adding to the existing local knowledge base, we expect that both a high overall *relatedness* and high *complementarity* of external knowledge inflows are conducive to a region's innovative activity.

We allow for two different types of knowledge inflows. *First*, and most importantly, we acknowledge the importance of the regional location in space and the existence of geographically bounded knowledge spillovers (Fischer et al., 2009; Jaffe et al., 1993) and are therefore interested in the *complementarity* and *relatedness* of the technological knowledge bases of neighbouring regions. In the following, we will refer to the measures as *spatial complementarity* and *spatial relatedness* respectively. *Second*, we build on recent findings of the geography of innovation literature, indicating that knowledge is increasingly transmitted in formal R&D networks (Wanzenböck & Piribauer, 2018) and analyse the impact of the technological relatedness to the knowledge bases of regions linked via R&D projects and the technological complementarity of the knowledge base of regions linked via R&D projects on the regions overall knowledge creation – in the following referred to as *network relatedness* and *network complementarity*.

Previous studies concerned about the role played by the characteristics of region-external knowledge, typically used trade data or patent citations to capture knowledge flows (see e.g., Miguelez & Moreno, 2018, Boschma et al., 2023; Sorenson et al., 2006). Particularly the use of patent citations has been criticized, as it is rather patent examiners than inventors, who include citations in patent documents (Breschi & Lissoni, 2005). Using data on common R&D projects allows us to capture knowledge spillovers arising from actual collaborations, while the consideration of spatially close regions allows us to shed light on the role played by the characteristics of spatially close regions – an aspect yet widely neglected in the empirical literature.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data & Variables

We conceptually start from a knowledge production framework, where the dependent variable is defined as logged regional knowledge stock k_{it} and proxied by patent data. Knowledge stock is specified as follows:

$$K_{it} = (1 - r_K) K_{it-1} + P_{it-1} \quad (1)$$

$$k_{it} = \log K_{it} \quad (2)$$

where knowledge stock K_{it} in region i is assumed to accumulate with newly produced knowledge P_{it-1} – proxied by annual patent applications of region i – and to depreciate at rate r_K ¹. For our analysis, we calculate the knowledge stock for the year 2019, using data spanning the period 2010-2019.

The main explanatory variables, as introduced in the conceptual framework in Section 2, encompass the concepts of *relatedness*, *complementarity* and *knowledge complexity*, and are designed to capture different aspects of the technological structure of both the region internal and region external knowledge base. The calculation is based on information on International Patent Classification (IPC) classes, provided in regional patent documents. We follow Pintar and Scherngell (2022) and employ the technological classification as proposed by Schmoch (2008), where the IPC classes are mapped onto 35 technology fields.

To capture the overall relatedness of a region’s knowledge base, we construct a measure for relatedness density for each region i and technology field k , closely following the work of Balland et al. (2019), based on the framework of product space of Hidalgo et al. (2007). *First*, we calculate relatedness between any two technology fields k and l ($\phi_{k,l}$), which is based on how often the technology pairs co-occurred on the same patent document in the period 2010-2014. We standardize the co-occurrence value according to the method of Steijn (2020), using the Econ Geo R package of Balland (2017)². *Second*, to determine to technology classes a region’s knowledge base consist of, i.e., in which technology classes a region is specialized in, we use the concept of revealed technological advantage (RTA). Region i has RTA in technology k if the share of technology k in the region’s patent portfolio is higher than the share of technology k in the patent portfolio aggregated over the whole sample. To ensure that a region does not have RTA based on a small total number of patents, we only allow a region to be specialized in technology k , if it has at least three fractionally counted patents in this field.

$$RTA_{i,k} = \begin{cases} 1, & \frac{X_{i,k}/\sum_k X_{i,k}}{\sum_i X_{i,k}/\sum_i \sum_k X_{i,k}} > 1 \text{ and } X_{i,k} \geq 3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$X_{i,k}$ reflects the number of patents in technology class k in region i . Based on the RTA measures and the relatedness values ($\phi_{k,l}$), we then calculate relatedness density (RD) for each technology k and each region i . It is defined as the sum of relatedness between technology k and all technologies l in which region i has RTA in, in relation to the sum of technological relatedness of technology k to all technologies present in the sample. To capture the overall relatedness of technologies present in region i , we follow Boschma et al. (2023) and take the average RD for all technologies k where region i is specialized, i.e., where $RTA_{ik} = 1$, where v refers to the number of technologies present in region i . For the sake of brevity, we will in the

¹ Following Caballero and Jaffe (1993), we assume a constant yearly depreciation rate r_K of 12%.

² The results are robust to different standardization methods.

following refer to this average RD of technologies present in a region as *relatedness*. Put formally:

$$RD_{k,i} = \frac{\sum_{l \neq k, k \in i} \phi_{k,l}}{\sum_{l \neq k} \phi_{k,l}} * 100 \quad (4)$$

$$Relatedness_i = \frac{1}{v} \sum_{k \in i}^v RD_{k,i} \quad (5)$$

The literature analysing the impact of technological relatedness on the regional innovation output has so far focused on entropy measures and hierarchical definitions of relatedness, using different levels of IPC codes or industries, where two fields are thought to be related when they fall under the same higher category (see e.g. Miguelez & Moreno, 2018). Our way of measuring technological relatedness allows us to also capture relatedness of technologies that are related, despite not belonging to the same higher category, and thus, to capture how close and distant *all* technologies a region is specialized in, are to each other.

The second variable of interest captures *spatial complementarity* and *network complementarity*, i.e., complementarities in technological knowledge of spatially close regions and regions connected via R&D collaborations, respectively. Calculating these indicators is a multi-step process. *First*, we follow Balland and Boschma (2021) and calculate for each pair of regions i and j and each technology k missing in region i ($RTA_{ik} = 0$), the amount of RD that can potentially be added by region j to the RD of region i in the respective technology k . This value reflects, to which extent region j is specialized in technologies l that are related to the missing technology k , and not present in region i . To retrieve the average RD region j can add to region i , i.e., the *complementarity* region j holds for region i , we average over all technologies k missing in region i , where x denotes the number of technologies missing in region i :

$$c_{ij} = \frac{1}{x} \sum_{k \notin i}^x \frac{\sum_{l \neq k, l \in j \wedge l \notin i} \phi_{k,l}}{\sum_{l \neq k} \phi_{k,l}} * 100 \quad (6)$$

For the *spatial complementarity* measure, we perform an element-wise multiplication of the n -by- n complementarity matrix C – reflecting the complementarity values for each pair of regions – by an n -by- n row standardized spatial weights matrix W and construct the row-sums $\sum(W \odot C)$. W describes the connectivity of spatial units, based on an 8 nearest neighbour definition of neighbourhood. Similarly, to capture *network complementarity*, we construct an n -by- n row standardized network matrix N , based on collaborative R&D projects of the European Framework programme (FP), which we multiply by matrix C , element by element and build row-sums $\sum(N \odot C)$ ³.

Similarly, to capture how related the knowledge base of region i is to the knowledge base of each linked region j , we calculate an n -by- n matrix, reflecting the bilateral relatedness for all

³ N is defined as a row-standardized weights matrix, where the ten regions with which a region shares the most European FP projects with are considered as linked regions. The links are weighted by the number of common FP projects. We also control for robustness of the results considering the links between regions arising from co-invention of patents.

pairs of regions, taking the average value of relatedness density of region i in technologies in which region j has RTA in, i.e., $bilateral\ relatedness_{i,j} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k \in j} RD_{k,i}$. Analogously to *spatial complementarity* and *network complementarity*, we calculate *spatial relatedness*, given by $\sum(W \odot bilateral\ relatedness)$ and *network relatedness*, given by $\sum(N \odot bilateral\ relatedness)$.

To calculate regional knowledge complexity, we employ methods of Hidalgo and Hausmann (2009), closely following Pintar and Scherngell (2022). Knowledge complexity captures both the diversity of a region's patent portfolio, given by $d_i = \sum_k RTA_{ik}$ and the ubiquity of the technologies, defined as $u_k = \sum_i RTA_{ik}$. The KCI for region i technology class u ($d_i^n; u_k^n$). can be derived by sequentially combining the measures of diversity and ubiquity, recursively refining them over a series of n iterations:

$$d_i^n = \frac{1}{d_i^0} \sum_k M_{ik} u_k^{(n-1)} \quad (7)$$

$$u_k^n = \frac{1}{u_k^0} \sum_i M_{ik} d_i^{(n-1)} \quad (8)$$

For the calculation, we use the EconGeo R package of Balland (2017), where the iterative process is reformulated as an eigenvector problem. By construction, a region with a high knowledge complexity is not only able produce knowledge in a large set of technological domains, but also in rare domains, which are assumed to be of high value for economic exploitation in the future.

We add different control variables to test the robustness of the estimates for our main independent variables, such as (i) logged degree centrality, reflecting R&D network effects, (ii) human resources, (iii) population, controlling for a region's size, and (iv) a metro-dummy variable, reflecting agglomeration economies and urbanization effects. Logged degree centrality is defined as the logged number of a region's network links (see Wasserman & Faust 1994) and constructed based on data on collaborative FP projects, retrieved from the EUPRO database, available via RISIS (risis2.eu). Data for the remaining control variables is drawn from Eurostat's regional database. Human resources are proxied by the share of persons with tertiary education and/or employed in science and technology (HRTS)⁴. Population is defined as the logged number of inhabitants. The metro-dummy takes the value of 1 if a region represents a metro region according to the NUTS-adapted classification. Summary statistics of the variables are shown in the Appendix in Table A1.

Our analysis covers 430 regions of current EU-27 countries, as well as Norway and the UK. We use the NUTS adapted regional classification developed by Lepori et al. (2019)⁵. For the

⁴ HRTS data is only available on NUTS2 level and was transformed to NUTS-adapted level assuming that all NUTS3 regions within a NUTS2 region share the same value with respect to HRTS.

⁵ The NUTS adapted classification is based on the aggregation of NUTS 3 regions of the NUTS 2016 classification. It includes Eurostat's metropolitan regions (aggregated NUTS 3 regions), and NUTS 2 regions for the remaining non-urban areas. A few NUTS3 regions with sizeable knowledge production, such as Oxford or Leuven, are singled out and enter on NUTS 3 level. This regional classification allows fine grained analysis of regions with sizable knowledge production, while still acknowledging the special role of metropolitan regions in knowledge production.

explanatory variables, we use data spanning the years 2010-2014, and aggregate it to smoothen yearly variation in the volatile patenting activity. The dependent variable knowledge stock is calculated for the year 2019, based on data reflecting the regional patenting activity spanning the years 2010-2019. Patent data is obtained from the OECD's REGPAT database⁶. We only consider regions that produced at least 50 fractionally counted patents in the period 2010-2014.

3.2. Model

To investigate drivers of regional knowledge creation, we employ a spatial Durbin model (SDM), conceptually building on a regional KPF framework. By doing so, we join a list of studies investigating the role played by the regional technological structure on knowledge creation. In contrast to most existing studies, our model augments the standard linear regression model by the spatially lagged dependent and spatially lagged independent variables, thereby accounting for the interconnectivity structure among regions and allowing for the estimation of local and global spatial externalities (LeSage & Pace, 2010). Put differently, the SDM approach helps us to capture spatial dependence of both the dependent and explanatory variables and thereby explore the role of spatial proximity for regional knowledge creation. For a set of regions $i, j = 1, \dots, n$, the baseline model is specified as:

$$k = \rho Wk + X\beta + \gamma Z + WX\theta + WZ\lambda + u \quad (9)$$

k is an n -dimensional vector reflecting technological knowledge production measured as the log of a region's knowledge stock as defined above. Wk is the dependent variable lagged in space, with ρ representing the spatial dependence parameter, and W the n -by- n row standardized spatial weights matrix that describes the connectivity of spatial units⁷. X is the n -by- m matrix capturing our main indicators of interest, as defined above, while Z is an n -by- l matrix, capturing the control variables, (with m and l indicating the number of respective variables). β and γ vectors of the corresponding coefficients. WX and WZ represent the spatial lags of variables captured in matrix X and Z , respectively, where θ and λ are the coefficient vectors associated with the spatial lags of X and Z . The model will be estimated for different variable combinations. Finally, u is the i.i.d. error term ($u \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I_N)$).

4. Empirical Results

Table 1 and Table 2 indicate the impact effects of the estimated SDMs for different model specifications. Due to feedback effects arising from the spatial dependence of the dependent variable, the interpretation of the estimated coefficients is not straightforward. Taking these feedback effects into account, we present the results of the estimated models in direct, indirect, and total effects, as suggested by LeSage and Pace (2010). The direct effect refers to the impact of a change in a certain explanatory variable in region i on its own logged knowledge stock. The indirect effect captures, how region i is affected by a change in the independent variable

⁶ We use geographic coordinates for the inventor locations provided by Rassenfosse et al. (2019) to allocate patents to the corresponding NUTS adapted regions. For patents where no geographic coordinates are available, we take NUTS 3 level provided by the original OECD REGPAT for the NUTS 2013 classification and use the Pmisc R package of Pintar (2022) to convert the regions to the NUTS 2016 classification.

⁷ We use an 8 nearest neighbour neighbourhood definition but also estimated the model with 4-12 nearest neighbour matrixes. The results remain stable.

of interest in neighbouring regions. The total effect is the sum of the direct and the indirect effect⁸.

Table 1: Impact estimates of the SDM

Dependent variable: Knowledge Stock (log), 2015-2019			
	<i>Model 1</i>	<i>Model 2</i>	<i>Model 3</i>
Direct effects			
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.012 ***	0.014 ***	0.008 **
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	0.024 ***	0.020 **	
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.014		0.017 *
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	0.000	-0.001	0.002
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	0.258 ***	0.249 ***	0.261 ***
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.040 ***	0.040 ***	0.041 ***
<i>Population (log)</i>	0.756 ***	0.757 ***	0.752 ***
<i>Metro Region</i>	0.173 **	0.163	0.181 **
Indirect effects			
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.044	0.081 ***	0.068 *
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	-0.028	-0.080	
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.036		0.009
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	-0.045 ***	-0.042 **	-0.047 ***
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	-0.412	-0.464	-0.395
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.043	0.041	0.038
<i>Population (log)</i>	-1.076 **	-1.085 **	-1.080 **
<i>Metro</i>	0.939	0.810	0.893
Total effects			
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.056	0.095 ***	0.076 *
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	-0.004	-0.060	
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.050		0.026
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	-0.045 **	-0.042 **	-0.045 ***
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	-0.154	-0.215	-0.134
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.083 **	0.080 **	0.079 **
<i>Population (log)</i>	-0.321	-0.328	-0.328
<i>Metro</i>	1.112	0.973	1.075
ρ (spatial parameter)	0.744 ***	0.742 ***	0.741 ***
AIC	787.9	785.58	799.56
Log Likelihood	-374.9	-375.79	-382.78

Notes: *** indicates significance at the 0.01 level, ** at the 0.05 level, and * at the 0.10 level, standard errors in brackets, spatial weights matrix constructed using k-nearest neighbours with $k = 8$, the number of observati

⁸ Table A 4 in the Appendix presents the respective estimated coefficients for different model specifications, while Table A 3 presents the coefficient of the OLS model.

ons for each model is 430, ρ denotes the coefficient of the dependent variable (it is not an impact estimate).

The results are highly interesting in the context of current debates on the drivers of regional knowledge production. Concerning the role played by characteristics of the local knowledge base, we make the following observations. *First*, as expected, we find that *relatedness* is significantly positively associated with a region's logged knowledge stock throughout all model specifications. This result supports the view that being specialized in related technologies facilitates the recombination of existing knowledge pieces, and thus stimulates regional technological knowledge creation. This is in line with the previous literature (see, for example, Miguelez & Moreno, 2018, Tavassoli & Carbonara, 2014; Castaldi et al., 2015), despite using a different estimation method, a different operationalization of the relatedness measure and different geographic scope. Against the background of regional convergence, these results indicate that moving towards a more interconnected knowledge domain constitutes a main catch-up opportunity for lagging regions. *Relatedness* is by construction positively correlated with the overall diversification of a region's knowledge space, i.e., the number of technologies the region has RTA in. To control for the possibility that our results are solely driven by a region's overall diversification, we estimate an additional model confirming that the effects of both specifications of relatedness are robust to the inclusion of diversification (see Appendix Table A 5). While diversification is significant and positive when it enters the model alone, it turns significantly negative when it enters together with relatedness of present technologies. This indicates that it is not diversification per se that is conducive to innovation, but rather the associated higher value in technological relatedness.

Second, for all our model specifications, we find a non-significant direct effect of *knowledge complexity*, suggesting that a large local knowledge stock is not necessarily a pre-condition for being able to produce knowledge in complex technologies. This result is interesting, given that the production of complex knowledge was recently discussed as a central source of competitive advantage for regions and firms (Balland et al., 2019) and implies that the development into a more complex knowledge space does not necessarily encourage an enlargement of the overall knowledge stock.

Turning to one of our core research-aims – namely the exploration of spatial dynamics of innovation, we find that spatial proximity indeed plays a central role in the process of technological knowledge creation. For one thing, the importance of spatial proximity is highlighted by the highly significant ρ coefficient, which confirms that the knowledge stock of a region is positively determined by the knowledge stocks of surrounding regions. This is in line with the literature (see e.g. Neuländtner & Scherngell, 2022; Wanzenböck & Piribauer, 2018) and suggests that there is indeed a geographical bias in knowledge spillovers.

Moreover, the impact estimates of model (1) and model (3) provide evidence of considerable positive effects of *spatial complementarity*, suggesting that the effect of spatial knowledge spillovers on a region's knowledge creation is not only determined by the size of the knowledge stock of spatially close regions (as indicated by the positive ρ coefficient), but also depends on the technological knowledge structure of these regions, more specifically on how complementary the knowledge domains of neighbouring regions are to the local knowledge

base (Boschma et al., 2017). The positive effect of *spatial complementarity* is in line with our hypotheses and indicates that regional innovative output benefits from extra-regional knowledge that is complementary, and not necessarily similar to, the local knowledge base. This indicates that external knowledge flows from neighbouring regions that provide access to technological knowledge in a field not present in a region, may stimulate regional knowledge production, providing the region with novel knowledge types, thus preventing it from a potential lock-in situation (Balland & Boschma, 2021). For *spatial relatedness*, we find a positive significant impact estimate in model (3). In principle, the positive effect of spatial relatedness supports the view that knowledge from related domains can more easily be absorbed and recombined with the own knowledge base. The effect, however, turns non-significant in model (1) once we control for *spatial complementarity*.

In terms of spatial lags of the explanatory variables, we find a significantly positive indirect effect of *relatedness* for the model specifications (2) and (3), indicating that regions do not only benefit from region-internal relatedness, but also from a high technological relatedness in neighbouring regions. While the direct effect of knowledge complexity is non-significant for most our model specifications, complexity exhibits a negative indirect effect, indicating that there are negative spatial spillover effects of knowledge complexity. The negative indirect effect is in line with the notion of complex knowledge as being characterized by low accessibility, a high degree of tacitness and, consequently, a pronounced spatial stickiness (Pintar & Scherngell, 2022), suggesting that regions cannot successfully tap complex knowledge sources from neighbouring regions.

Moreover, acknowledging that knowledge spillovers do not only occur between spatially close agents, but also via R&D networks, model (4) - (6) present the effect of technological relatedness and complementarity of regions connected to local agents via shared R&D projects. *Network complementarity* – reflecting the average technological complementarity of the ten regions a region shares the most, common European FP projects with, exhibits both significant positive direct and indirect effects, that are even higher in magnitude than the impacts estimated for *spatial complementarity*. Both, model (4) and model (6), yield a positive yet statistically insignificant effect for *network relatedness*, suggesting that regions do not benefit more from R&D collaborations with regions possessing a related technological knowledge base.

As what concerns the control variables, our estimates are in line with previous works (see e.g. Wanzenböck & Piribauer, 2018; Autant-Bernard et al., 2007). We find positive direct effects for *degree centrality*. The negative indirect effect associated with *degree centrality* – indicating that being located close to regions that are well embedded in collaborative R&D links hinders, rather than stimulates, one's own regional patenting activity – is counterintuitive to the idea of spatial spillovers. However, it can be explained by the presence of individual regions, with both particularly high knowledge stocks and high embeddedness in the R&D network, that are surrounded by regions with low levels of knowledge stock and a low *degree centrality*. As expected, we find positive and significant direct effects for both *human resources* and *population*. The latter serves as an agglomeration measure to control for the size of a region. We also find significantly positive direct effects for the metro region dummy variable, reflecting the increased innovation activity in urban areas, which are typically characterized by a higher firm and university density.

Table 2: Impact estimates of the SDM

Dependent variable: Knowledge Stock (log), 2015-2019			
	<i>Model 4</i>	<i>Model 5</i>	<i>Model 6</i>
Direct effects			
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.011***	0.012***	0.009***
<i>Network complementarity</i>	0.029***	0.028***	
<i>Network relatedness</i>	0.007		0.010
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	-0.001	-0.002	0.002
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	0.328***	0.331***	0.348***
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.039***	0.039***	0.040***
<i>Population</i>	0.732***	0.725***	0.728***
<i>Metro Region</i>	0.146*	0.135*	0.142*
Indirect effects			
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.084***	0.087***	0.090***
<i>Network complementarity</i>	0.010	-0.004	
<i>Network relatedness</i>	0.139		0.115
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	-0.039**	-0.049***	-0.040**
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	-0.423	-0.366	-0.408
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.032	0.033	0.031
<i>Population</i>	-0.962**	-1.038**	-0.984**
<i>Metro</i>	1.002	0.877	1.113
Total effects			
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.095***	0.099***	0.098***
<i>Network complementarity</i>	0.039	0.024	
<i>Network relatedness</i>	0.147		0.124
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	-0.040**	-0.050***	-0.038**
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	-0.095	-0.034	-0.060
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.071*	0.071**	0.071**
<i>Population (log)</i>	-0.230	-0.313	-0.256
<i>Metro</i>	1.148	1.012	1.255
ρ (spatial parameter)	0.760***	0.757***	0.760***
AIC	787.94	785.59	799.56
Log Likelihood	-374.97	-375.79	-382.78

Notes: *** indicates significance at the 0.01 level, ** at the 0.05 level, and * at the 0.10 level, standard errors in brackets, spatial weights matrix constructed using k-nearest neighbours with $k = 8$, the number of observations for each model is 430, ρ denotes the coefficient of the dependent variable (it is not an impact estimate).

5. Illustrating convergence potentials

The empirical results described in the previous section pave the way for using these estimates to illustrate potentials for reducing inequalities in regional innovation capacity across Europe.

We shift our attention to *relatedness*, *spatial complementarity*, and *network complementarity* – our main technological indicators of interest for which we could identify a significant and positive impact. The aim is to capture the potentials these variables yield for reducing spatial inequalities across regions in terms of technological knowledge stock⁹. We do so by using the direct and indirect impact estimates of the SDM as presented in Table 1 and Table 2. To demonstrate their relevance in explaining the observed disparities in regional knowledge stocks, and thus, to illustrate potential convergence pathways, we calculate the regional knowledge stock per million inhabitants as predicted by the model estimates, while synthetically increasing the values of the variables of interest in lagging regions¹⁰. In the following simulations, lagging regions are defined as all regions with a knowledge stock per million below the median¹¹.

Figure 1: Predicted Gini Coefficient across regions in terms of knowledge stock per million if lagging regions close x% of their gap to highest observed value in the respective explanatory variable.

Figure 1 illustrates the evolution of overall regional inequality – measured by the Gini index across regions, in terms of the predicted stock of knowledge per million inhabitants. Hereby, the assumption is that all lagging regions gradually increase their value in the respective variable, until they reach the highest empirically observed value of *relatedness*, *spatial complementarity* or *network complementarity* respectively, or put differently, until they close 100% of the gap in the respective variable. As implied by their positive impact estimates, all selected variables yield a certain potential to reduce regional disparities. The decrease in the Gini coefficient starts to decline when increasing the values of *relatedness* based on the impact

⁹ As our results suggest that there is no positive association between knowledge complexity, *network relatedness*, *spatial relatedness* and knowledge stock, we omit these variables in the following simulation.

¹⁰ Adjusting for population when analysing heterogeneity of regional knowledge stocks, allows to control for differences in size.

¹¹ Simulations for alternative groups of lagging regions can be found in the Appendix in Figure A 4, where *Q1* regions include all regions in the lowest quartile of knowledge stock per million inhabitants, *Q2* regions refer to all regions above the first quartile but below the median. The groups of lagging regions are plotted in

estimates of model 4, suggesting that as the value of the variable increases, some formerly lagging regions overtake the non-lagging regions in terms of their population adjusted knowledge stock.

Figure 2 for *relatedness*, Figure 3 for *spatial complementarity* and Figure 4 for *network complementarity*, show the predicted spatial distribution of the regional knowledge stock per million in relation to the average knowledge stock per million inhabitants across all regions, (a) based on the observed empirical values of the explanatory variables, after the lagging regions have closed (b) 30%, (c) 60% and (d) 100% of the gap to the highest observed value of the respective variable. By how the plotted variables are constructed, all regions would take a value of one if knowledge stock per million was equally distributed across regions. Map (a) indicates that the predicted stock of knowledge per million, based on empirical explanatory variables, tends to be low in southern and eastern European regions, while central European regions – particularly regions in southern Germany – are characterized by predicted values of knowledge stock per million that are up to six times as high as the European average. When the explanatory variable of interest is synthetically increased step by step, lagging regions gradually catch-up with stronger regions. This convergence process is visible for all plotted variables, but strongest for *spatial complementarity*. While the predicted regional share of the average knowledge stock per million is as low as 0.03 times the European average for some Polish and southern Italian regions in the baseline scenario (a), all lagging regions reach a knowledge stock equivalent to at least one third of the European average in scenario (d).

Figure 2 Spatial distribution of predicted regional knowledge stock per million in relation to the regional knowledge stock per million averaged over all observations, when lagging regions close the gap to the highest observed value of *relatedness*. Simulation based on

impacts of model (1) in Table 1.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of predicted regional knowledge stock per million in relation to the regional knowledge stock per million averaged over all observations, when lagging regions close the gap to the highest observed value of spatial complementarity. Simulation based on impacts of model (1) in Table 1.

Figure 4 Spatial distribution of predicted regional knowledge stock per million in relation to the regional knowledge stock per million averaged over all observations, when lagging regions close the gap to the highest observed value of *network complementarity*. Simulation based on impacts of model (4) in Table 2.

We want to stress that the simulations only represent descriptive scenarios to explore the impact of the observed variables on regional inequality in terms of technological knowledge creation. Particularly the *spatial complementarity* value, which is given externally by the location of the region, is nothing the region can directly influence.

6. Conclusion

Local knowledge endowments are widely regarded as the fundamental basis of a region's innovative capacity, and accordingly, viewed as a major source of spatial inequalities in innovation and, hence, economic competitiveness in the long run. While the concepts of

knowledge complexity, technological relatedness and complementarity of external knowledge bases have been widely discussed conceptually (e.g., Balland & Rigby, 2017; Boschma et al., 2015) and have recently also been studied empirically, mostly to explain regional paths of technological development (e.g., Balland & Boschma, 2021; Balland et al., 2019), there is still little understanding of how relevant they are for explaining regional disparities in terms of regional knowledge production, particularly against the background of spatial dependence across regions.

In an attempt to fill this gap and to explore the role played by spatial proximity, we estimated a spatial Durbin model for 430 European regions, investigating the effect of the region-internal technological structure – captured by concepts of relatedness or complexity – on the regional patenting output, while also analysing the role played by the characteristics of region external technological knowledge bases, acknowledging that external knowledge flows constitute a central driver of local innovative activity. Hereby, we considered the complementarity and relatedness of both spatially close regions and regions connected via common R&D projects, and their impact on the local knowledge stock.

The results are highly interesting, both in terms of advancing the literature on drivers for regional inequalities, but also in a policy context pointing to important dimensions as what concerns the identification of potentials for reducing inequalities in innovation. First, we find that the regional-internal technological relatedness is a significant and important driver of regional knowledge production, and accordingly can act as important lever for regions to catch-up. Second, the complementarity of a region's knowledge base to that of connected regions – spatially or via network channels – is an even more important determinant to increase a region's innovative capability. Third, increasing the complexity of a region's knowledge base does not affect its overall knowledge production intensity, but just its specificity in certain, more complex technologies. Clearly, this may trigger positive economic effects in terms of productivity and growth, but is in this sense not a vehicle to decrease inequalities across regions in overall innovative capabilities. Fourth, spatial spillovers are an extremely important driver for regional knowledge production, and therefore – though so far largely neglected – a very important driver regional inequality. This is also reflected by agglomeration effects that are at stake, showing that metro-regions benefit from cumulative, localized effects that is not existent for non-metro regions.

Applying our findings against the background of regional disparities in innovative capacities, we find that the estimated effects point to different convergence scenarios, i.e., potential pathways for lagging regions to catch-up and to strengthen their overall innovative capacity. As suggested by the positive effect of network complementarity, one promising pathway clearly lies in the development of strategic links with regions with technologically complementary capabilities to access knowledge in technologies that are lacking in the region. An alternative potential for catching-up could be generated by a more targeted development of capacities in technologies related to the current knowledge base. A combination of both, i.e., increasing complementarity and regional-internal technological relatedness, generates the highest convergence potential.

These results are not only interesting in advancing the literature on drivers for regional inequality but are also highly relevant for policy debates which raise the reduction of such inequalities to top of the current agenda. First, simulating convergence scenarios, we find the greatest potential for lagging regions to catch-up by increasing their technological relatedness, on the one hand, and their technological complementarity to the knowledge bases of connected regions, on the other hand. Accordingly, policies at different level (regional, national, European) should shift specific attention to those two dimensions. Second, given the positive effect of complementarity when connected via networks, disadvantages related to spatial distance can be overcome by enhancing the networking intensity of a region with other regions. Thus, regional and national science and innovation policies have to put an even stronger focus on enabling regions to participate in such networks, e.g., via respective education programs or funding of related and complementary technologies. Third, while smart specialization policies to diversify into complex technologies may be useful for regions with already some substantial innovative capabilities, it is not a promising transition path for lagging regions. They should first put emphasis on enhancing their relatedness and complementarity to decrease their gap to more advanced regions in overall innovative capabilities.

Table A 1 Correlation of independent variables.

	Related-ness	Complexity	Spatial complementarity	Network complementarity	Spatial relatedness	Network relatedness	Diversification	Population (log)	Human Resources (HRST)	Degree centrality (log)
<i>Relatedness</i>	1	0.19	-0.24	-0.02	0.14	0.04	0.75	0.22	0.21	0.3
<i>Complexity</i>	0.19	1	0.32	0.3	-0.18	-0.16	0.12	0.2	0.23	0.31
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	-0.24	0.32	1	0.39	-0.06	-0.10	-0.50	0.01	0.13	0.00
<i>Network complementarity</i>	-0.02	0.30	0.39	1	0.11	0.17	-0.37	0.06	0.21	0.30
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.14	-0.18	-0.06	0.11	1	0.1	-0.06	-0.03	0.00	0.02
<i>Network relatedness</i>	0.04	-0.16	-0.10	0.17	0.1	1	0.04	-0.03	0.06	0.21
<i>Diversification</i>	0.75	0.12	-0.5	-0.37	-0.06	0.04	1	0.19	0.12	0.24
<i>Population (log)</i>	0.22	0.20	0.01	0.06	-0.03	-0.03	0.19	1	0.01	0.30
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.21	0.23	0.13	0.21	0.00	0.06	0.12	0.01	1	0.22
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	0.30	0.31	0.00	0.30	0.02	0.21	0.24	0.3	0.22	1

Appendix

Table A 2: Summary statistics

	N	Min	Mean	Median	Max	SD	Period
<i>Knowledge stock (log)</i>	430	4.15	6.48	6.49	10.47	1.22	2010-2019
<i>Relatedness</i>	430	10.94	39.86	39.76	64.87	10.53	2010-2014
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	430	9.13	20.10	19.92	36.85	4.74	2010-2014
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	430	22.25	35.84	35.61	56.71	4.97	2010-2014
<i>Network complementarity</i>	430	0.00	23.49	23.22	38.36	4.45	2010-2014
<i>Network relatedness</i>	430	0.00	34.55	34.49	43.94	3.94	2010-2014
<i>Complexity</i>	430	0.00	29.69	28.22	100.00	17.18	2010-2014
<i>Diversification</i>	430	3.00	11.61	12.00	19.00	2.77	2010-2014
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	430	0.00	5.20	5.40	6.20	0.80	2010-2014
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	430	15.00	31.68	32.24	51.64	6.57	2010-2014
<i>Population (log)</i>	430	11.48	13.56	13.50	16.41	0.72	2010-2014

Figure A 1: Spatial distribution of control variables

Figure A 2: Spatial distribution of the main indicators

Figure A 3: Regions in the first and second quartile (Q2) with respect to their knowledge stock per million inhabitants

Table A 3: Coefficients of the OLS Model

OLS Model Coefficients, Dependent variable: Knowledge Stock (log), 2015-2019)						
	OLS 1	OLS 2	OLS 3	OLS 4	OLS 5	OLS 6
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.025*** (0.005)	0.021*** (0.005)	0.035*** (0.007)	0.024*** (0.005)	0.024*** (0.005)	0.032*** (0.007)
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	0.024** (0.011)	0.020* (0.010)	0.009 (0.012)			
<i>Network complementarity</i>				0.032*** (0.011)	0.032*** (0.011)	0.017 (0.015)
<i>Complexity</i>	-0.018*** (0.003)	-0.015*** (0.003)	-0.017*** (0.003)	-0.018*** (0.003)	-0.018*** (0.003)	-0.017*** (0.003)
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>		0.034*** (0.009)				
<i>Network relatedness</i>					0.002 (0.015)	
<i>Diversification</i>			-0.064** (0.028)			-0.050 (0.032)
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	0.303*** (0.069)	0.286*** (0.068)	0.303*** (0.068)	0.336*** (0.078)	0.336*** (0.078)	0.345*** (0.078)
<i>HR (HRST)</i>	0.070*** (0.007)	0.071*** (0.007)	0.071*** (0.007)	0.068*** (0.007)	0.068*** (0.007)	0.069*** (0.007)
<i>Population (log)</i>	0.473*** (0.071)	0.493*** (0.070)	0.479*** (0.070)	0.461*** (0.071)	0.461*** (0.071)	0.464*** (0.071)
<i>Metro</i>	0.242** (0.095)	0.257*** (0.094)	0.243** (0.095)	0.227** (0.096)	0.227** (0.096)	0.225** (0.096)
<i>Constant</i>	-4.770*** (0.946)	-6.059*** (0.998)	-4.297*** (0.964)	-4.943*** (0.944)	-5.025*** (-5.025)	-4.514*** (0.980)
<i>Observations</i>	430	430	430	428	428	428
<i>R2</i>	0.420	0.437	0.427	0.423	0.423	0.427
<i>Adjusted R2</i>	0.410	0.426	0.416	0.414	0.412	0.416
<i>Residual Std. Error</i>	0.918	0.905	0.914	0.914	0.915	0.912

Notes: Data on explanatory variables are significant at the $p < 0.1^*$; $p < 0.05^{**}$; $p < 0.01^{***}$ level. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table A 4: Coefficients of the SDM Model

SDM Model Coefficients, Dependent variable: Knowledge Stock (log), 2015-2019								
	SDM 1	SDM 2	SM 3	SDM 4	SDM 5	SDM 6	SDM 7	SDM 8
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.01***	0.01***	0.01*	0.02***	0.01**	0.01***	0.01*	0.02***
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	0.03***	0.02***		0.01				
<i>Network complementarity</i>					0.03***	0.03***		0.01
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.01		0.02**					
<i>Network relatedness</i>					0.00		0.01	
<i>Complexity</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00*	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Diversification</i>				-0.06				-0.05
<i>Degree centrality</i>	0.28***	0.27***	0.28***	0.28***	0.35***	0.35***	0.37***	0.36***
<i>HR (HRST)</i>	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***
<i>Population (log)</i>	0.80***	0.80***	0.80***	0.80***	0.77***	0.77***	0.77***	0.77***
<i>Metro</i>	0.13**	0.13**	0.14**	0.14**	0.10*	0.10	0.10	0.10
<i>SL: Relatedness</i>	0.00	0.01*	0.01	0.01	0.02**	0.02**	0.02***	0.00
<i>SL: Spatial complementarity</i>	-0.03	-0.04**		-0.02				
<i>SL: Network complementarity</i>					-0.02	-0.02		0.00
<i>SL: Spatial relatedness</i>	0.00		-0.01					
<i>SL: Network relatedness</i>					0.03		0.03	
<i>SL: Complexity</i>	-0.01***	-0.01***	-0.02***	-0.01***	-0.01**	-0.01***	-0.01***	-0.01***
<i>SL: Diversification</i>				0.05				0.07
<i>SL: Degree</i>	-0.31***	-0.32***	-0.31***	-0.33***	-0.37***	-0.36***	-0.38***	-0.36***
<i>SL: Human)</i>	-0.02	-0.02*	-0.02*	-0.02**	-0.02*	-0.02*	-0.02**	-0.02**
<i>SL: Population</i>	-0.88***	-0.89***	-0.88***	-0.88***	-0.83***	-0.85***	-0.84***	-0.85***
<i>SL: Metro</i>	0.15	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.17	0.15	0.22	0.17
<i>Constant</i>	1.43	1.92	1.48	1.78	-0.38	1.18	0.00	1.00
ρ (spatial parameter)	0.74***	0.74***	0.74***	0.75***	0.76***	0.76***	0.76***	0.75***
<i>Observations</i>	430	430	430	430.00	428	428	428	428
<i>Log Likelihood</i>	-381.8	-382.9	-388.6	-378.00	-375.0	-375.8	-382.8	-371.6
σ^2	0.32	0.32	0.33	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.32	0.30
<i>AIC</i>	801.8	800.0	811.3	793.90	787.9	785.6	799.6	781.3

Notes: Data on explanatory variables are significant at the $p < 0.1^*$; $p < 0.05^{**}$; $p < 0.01^{***}$ level. SL refers to the spatial lag of the respective variable. The spatial weights matrix W is constructed using 8-nearest neighbours

Table A 5: Impact estimates SDM, controlled for diversification

Dependent variable: Knowledge Stock (log), 2015-2019				
	Model A1	Model A2	Model A3	Model A4

Direct effects				
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.02**	0.02***	0.02***	0.02***
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	0.01	0.00		
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.01			
<i>Network complementarity</i>			0.01	0.01
<i>Network relatedness</i>			0.01	
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	0.00	-0.06	0.00	0.00
<i>Diversification</i>	-0.05**	0.00	-0.05**	-0.05**
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	0.34***	0.26***	0.34***	0.34***
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***	0.04***
<i>Population (log)</i>	0.74***	0.76***	0.74***	0.73***
<i>Metro Region</i>	0.15*	0.17	0.15*	0.14*
Indirect effects				
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.06	0.09**	0.06	0.07
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	0.04	-0.06		
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.16			
<i>Network complementarity</i>			0.04	0.02
<i>Network relatedness</i>			0.16	
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	-0.04**	0.00	-0.04**	-0.05
<i>Diversification</i>	0.14	-0.04**	0.14	0.11
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	-0.43	-0.46	-0.43	-0.37
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
<i>Population (log)</i>	-0.95**	-1.07**	-0.95**	-1.03**
<i>Metro</i>	1.13	0.85	1.13	0.99
Total effects				
<i>Relatedness</i>	0.08	0.11**	0.08	0.09*
<i>Spatial complementarity</i>	0.06	-0.05		
<i>Spatial relatedness</i>	0.17			
<i>Network complementarity</i>			0.06	0.03
<i>Network relatedness</i>			0.16	
<i>Knowledge complexity</i>	-0.04**	-0.06	-0.04**	-0.05***
<i>Diversification</i>	0.09	-0.04**	0.09	0.06
<i>Degree centrality (log)</i>	-0.10	-0.20	-0.10	-0.03
<i>Human Resources (HRST)</i>	0.07*	0.08**	0.07*	0.07*
<i>Population (log)</i>	-0.21	-0.31	-0.21	-0.30
<i>Metro</i>	1.28	1.03	1.28	1.13
ρ (spatial parameter)	0.75***	0.75***	0.76***	0.76***
N	430	430	428	428
AIC	797.90	794.00	783.1	781.30
Log Likelihood	-377.90	-378.00	-370.5	-371.60

Notes: Data on explanatory variables are significant at the $p < 0.1^*$; $p < 0.05^{**}$; $p < 0.01^{***}$ level., spatial weights matrix constructed using k-nearest neighbours with $k = 8$.

Figure A 4: Predicted Gini Coefficient across regions in terms of knowledge stock per million if lagging regions close x% of their gap to highest observed value in the respective explanatory variable.

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